

A DTW-BASED SCORE FOLLOWING METHOD FOR SCORE-INFORMED SOUND SOURCE SEPARATION

F.J. Rodriguez-Serrano

F.J. Canadas-Quesada

Universidad de Jaen

{fjrodrig, fcanadas}@ujaen.es

J. Menendez-Canal

R. Cortina

Universidad de Oviedo

raquel@uniovi.es

jonatanmenendez@gmail.com

A. Vidal

Universidad Politecnica de Valencia

avidal@dsic.upv.es

ABSTRACT

Along this work, a new online Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) based score alignment method is used over an online score-informed source separation system. The proposed alignment stage deals with the input signal and the score. It estimates the score position of each new audio frame in an online fashion by using only information from the beginning of the signal up to the present audio frame. Then, under the Non-negative Matrix Factorization (NMF) framework and previously learned instrument models the different instrument sources are separated. The instrument models are learned on training excerpts of the same kinds of instruments. Experiments are performed to evaluate the proposed system and its individual components. Results show that it outperforms a state-of-the-art comparison method.

1. INTRODUCTION

The goal of Sound Source Separation (SSS) is to segregate constituent sound sources from an audio signal mixture. The SSS task is of interest because a lot of direct user applications can be developed with it. Personalizing a live concert by letting the listener adjust the volume of individual instruments is one application of online SSS. Music education applications can be developed with both offline and online SSS methods.

There are some types of information that can be introduced in the SSS process. Spectral information can be introduced by using instrument models when the instruments are known in advance [1]. Also, musical score information can be used if the score and audio are well aligned [2].

The problem of audio-to-score alignment (or score matching) is the task of synchronizing an audio recording of a musical piece with the corresponding symbolic score. In offline alignment, the whole performance is accessible for the alignment process, i.e. it allows us to “look into the future” while establishing the matching. Online alignment, also known as score following, processes the data in realtime as the signal is acquired.

In this paper we deal with the problem of online score-informed separation of harmonic musical sources from a single-channel recording. We combine a novel audio-score alignment model with the Multi-excitation per Instrument (MEI) NMF model proposed in [3] to build the whole informed separation system. In a previous work [4], this schedule is used with a different alignment method [2]. We then advance this system by using our own alignment method which has a reduced computational complexity and, in the future, could be implemented on devices with limited resources. Therefore, our final system takes a music score and pre-learned instrument models as prior information, aligns the score with the audio and separates the audio mixture, all completed in an online fashion.

In the experiments, we show that the proposed online algorithm separates sources almost as well as the offline version of the algorithm and the proposed alignment method outperform those published in [4].

1.1 Related Work

There are some online approaches for source separation under the NMF-SSS framework [5–7]. However, [5, 6] were only tested in speech enhancement applications as they were designed to adapt one source (speech or noise) but keeping the other source fixed during separation. In our proposal, multiple instruments are learned and separated. The method proposed in [7] is suitable for multi-channel signals, but not for monaural ones. The mixing information (which represents the spatial information) is very important for their system. Also, random initialization of the model parameters without any extra information would make it difficult to discriminate between the different sources at monaural sources. To date, none of these approaches [5–7] have been applied to work in the score-informed source separation setting.

Audio-to-score alignment is traditionally performed in two steps: feature extraction and alignment. On the one hand, the features extracted from the audio signal characterize some specific information about the musical content. On the other hand, the alignment is performed by finding the best match between the feature sequence and the score. In fact, classical offline systems rely on cost measures between events in the score and in the performance. Two well known methods in speech recognition have been extensively used in the literature: statistical approaches (e.g. HMMs) [2], and DTW [8]. Although these techniques

achieve good results, their best performances are obtained in offline applications; the results decrease significantly for real-time audio-to-score alignment.

The present work is based on [4], where an online score-informed source separation system is proposed. This work uses a previously proposed alignment stage [5] to inform a SSS algorithm with adaptive instrument models. Here, we are going to use our own alignment method to supervise this separation process. The model adaptation stage proposed in [4] has been suppressed because the aim of this work is to assess the proposed alignment method while the NMF-based source separation algorithm is used by the same way. Summarizing, only previously trained instrument models will be applied over the NMF-based SSS algorithm which will be score-informed by a new score alignment stage.

Besides [2], there are several other online polyphonic audio-score alignment methods [8, 9]. We compare the proposed alignment method, applied over a SSS system, versus the one proposed in [2] because it is designed to align multi-instrument polyphonic music audio with score information and it has been tested on multi-instrumental polyphonic audio with clear objective measures. Despite the fact that the proposal of [8] is tested over piano music and multi instrument signals, its performance is not evaluated over multi instrument signals with objective results, due to the lack of reliable annotations. Other methods are only designed for, or tested on, [9] single-instrument polyphonic audio.

2. BACKGROUND

In this section the methods from the bibliography that the proposed system builds on are summarized. The aim of the proposed work is to introduce a DTW-based online Score Following method in a previous SSS algorithm. The SSS algorithm uses an NMF framework initialized with the score information for the activations and previously trained instrument models for the spectral patterns. This complete framework has been suitably modified to be able to segregate the individual signals in an online manner.

2.1 Instrument models

The instrument model used in the current work is *Multi-Excitation per Instrument* (MEI) model [3]. Let $X(t, f)$ be the true time-frequency representation of an audio mixture (e.g. a recording of several musical instruments), where t is time and f is a frequency of analysis. Let $\hat{X}(t, f)$ be an estimate of the true mixture. We define a spectral basis function $b(f)$ as a function that outputs the relative amplitudes of each frequency. We use spectral basis functions to represent the instantaneous timbre of sound sources, like musical instruments. If the timbre of an instrument is different in different situations (e.g. when a musical instrument plays different pitches) multiple spectral basis functions (one per pitch) can be associated with the instrument.

The MEI framework tries to decompose $\hat{X}(t, f)$ of the audio mixture into a linear combination of spectral basis function:

$$X(t, f) \approx \hat{X}(t, f) = \sum_{j=1}^J \sum_{n=1}^N g_{n,j}(t) b_{n,j}(f) \quad (1)$$

where $b_{n,j}(f)$ is the n -th basis for the j -th instrument; $g_{n,j}(t)$ is its gain at frame t . When dealing with harmonic instrument sounds in this paper, each spectral basis function ideally corresponds to a pitch, and the gain represents the activation strength of the pitch.

The signal model used at the SSS stage, where only $g_{n,j}(t)$ are estimated, is the one described in (1). However, the way of getting the basis $b_{n,j}(f)$, which are not computed into the SSS stage, needs a more complex signal model which is summarized here, but it is fully explained in [3].

The multi-excitation model proposed by Carabias et al. in [3] is an extension of the regular excitation-filter model presented in [10]. This model defines the excitation spectrum as a linear combination of a few excitation basis vectors. Under the multi-excitation model, the excitation per pitch and instrument is defined as

$$b_{n,j}(f) = h_j(f) \sum_m \left(\sum_i w_{i,n,j} v_{i,m,j} \right) G(f - m f_0(n)) \quad (2)$$

where $m = 1, \dots, M$ is the index of the harmonics; and $i = 1, \dots, I$ is the index of excitation basis vectors ($I \ll N$). $v_{i,m,j}$ is the m -th harmonic of the i -th excitation basis vector for instrument j ; $w_{i,n,j}$ is the weight of the i -th excitation basis vector for pitch n and instrument j . $G(f - m f_0(n))$ is the window transform placed at the frequency of the m -th harmonic of the n -th pitch.

Given the MEI model, the magnitude spectra of the mixture signal can be decomposed by substituting Eq. (2) into Eq. (1):

$$\hat{X}(t, f) = \sum_{n,m,i,j} g_{n,j}(t) h_j(m f_0(n)) w_{i,n,j} v_{i,m,j} G(f - m f_0(n)) \quad (3)$$

2.2 NMF parameter estimation

Once the signal model is presented, the way to compute the estimation of each parameter from both the instrument model and the SSS stage should be described. The same NMF framework used in [4] is applied. Given the model in Eq. (3), we want to estimate the parameters so that the reconstruction error between the observed spectrogram $X(t, f)$ and the modeled one $\hat{X}(t, f)$ is minimized. The β -divergence [11, 12] is used here as the cost function to define the reconstruction error, where β is in the range of $[0, 2]$. In [4], a study of the separation performance in function of the parameter β is shown, so that the same $\beta = 1.5$ is used here.

In [13], an iterative algorithm based on multiplicative update rules is proposed to obtain the model parameters that minimize the cost function. Under these rules, $D_\beta(X_t(f) \| \hat{X}_t(f))$ is non-increasing at each iteration and the non-negativity of the bases and the gains is ensured. The multiplicative update rule (see [13] for further details)

for each scalar parameter θ_l is given by expressing the partial derivatives of the $\nabla_{\theta_l} D_\beta$ as the quotient of two positive terms $\nabla_{\theta_l}^- D_\beta$ and $\nabla_{\theta_l}^+ D_\beta$:

$$\theta_l \leftarrow \theta_l \frac{\nabla_{\theta_l}^- D_\beta(X(t, f) || \hat{X}(t, f))}{\nabla_{\theta_l}^+ D_\beta(X(t, f) || \hat{X}(t, f))}. \quad (4)$$

assuming $\nabla_{\theta_l} D = \nabla_{\theta_l}^+ D - \nabla_{\theta_l}^- D$. The main advantage of the multiplicative update rule in Eq. (4) is that non-negativity of the bases and the gains is ensured, resulting in a NMF algorithm.

2.3 Dynamic Time Warping for Score Alignment

In this paper we will use a low complexity signal decomposition method that obtains a distortion matrix for each combination of notes per frame. This matrix is directly used by an online Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) algorithm to obtain the best path without having any information from the future. Consequently, a brief review of DTW is presented below.

DTW is a technique for aligning time series or sequences which has been intensively applied by the speech recognition community [14, 15] and used in many fields such as data mining [16] and information retrieval. The series are represented by 2 vectors of features $U = u_1, \dots, u_i, \dots, u_I$ and $V = v_1, \dots, v_j, \dots, v_J$ where i and j are the point indices in the time series. I and J represent the length of time series U and V , respectively. As a dynamic programming technique, it divides the problem into several sub-problems, each of which contribute in calculating the distance (or cost function) cumulatively.

The first stage in the DTW algorithm is to fill a local distance matrix (a.k.a cost matrix) \mathbf{D} as follows:

$$D(i, j) = \psi(u_i, v_j) \quad (5)$$

where matrix \mathbf{D} has $I \times J$ elements which represent the match cost between every two points in the time series. The cost function ψ could be any cost function that returns cost 0 for a perfect match, and a positive value otherwise (e.g. euclidean distance).

In the second stage (forward step), a warping matrix \mathbf{C} is filled recursively as:

$$C(i, j) = \min \left\{ \begin{array}{l} C(i, j - c_j) + D(i, j) \\ C(i - c_i, j) + D(i, j) \\ C(i - c_i, j - c_j) + \sigma D(i, j) \end{array} \right\} \quad (6)$$

where c_i and c_j are step size at each dimension and range from 1 to α_i and 1 to α_j , respectively. α_i and α_j are the maximum step size at each dimension. Parameter σ controls the bias toward diagonal steps. $C(i, j)$ is the cost of the minimum cost path from $(1, 1)$ to (i, j) , and $C(1, 1) = D(1, 1)$.

Finally, in the last stage (traceback step), the minimum cost path $\mathbf{w} = w_1, \dots, w_k, \dots, w_K$ is obtained by tracing the recursion backwards from $C(I, J)$. Each w_k is an ordered pair (i_k, j_k) such that $(i, j) \in \mathbf{w}$ means that the points u_i and v_j are aligned. The cost of a path $C(\mathbf{w})$ is the sum of the local match costs of the path:

$$C(\mathbf{w}) = \sum_{k=1}^K C(i_k, j_k) \quad (7)$$

3. ALIGNMENT METHOD

3.1 States Definition

The aim of this section is to adequately organize the information given by the score to be used for alignment purposes.

First of all, the binary ground-truth transcription matrix $\mathbf{GT}(n, \tau)$ is inferred from the MIDI score, where τ is the time in frames referenced to the score (MIDI time) and n are the notes in MIDI scale. The score defines a consecutive sequence of M states. Each state m is defined by its combination of notes (for all instruments). There are only K unique combination of notes in a score where $K \leq M$ because some states are composed by the same combination of notes.

From the ground-truth transcription matrix $\mathbf{GT}(n, \tau)$, we obtain the following decomposition of binary matrices

$$\mathbf{GT}(n, \tau) = \mathbf{Q}(n, k)\mathbf{R}(k, \tau) \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbf{Q}(n, k)$ is the notes-to-combination matrix, k the index of each unique combination of notes and $\mathbf{R}(k, \tau)$ represents the activation of each combination in MIDI time. This matrix contains the notes belonging to each combination but no information about MIDI time. Conversely, $\mathbf{R}(k, \tau)$ matrix retains the MIDI time activation per combination but no information about the notes active per combination.

3.2 Spectral Patterns Learning

When a signal frame is given to a DTW-based score follower, the first step should be the computation of a similarity measure between the current frame and the different combinations of notes defined by the score. Our approach is to compute a distortion between the frequency transform of the input and just one spectral pattern per combination of notes. A spectral pattern is here defined as a fixed spectrum which is learned from a signal with certain characteristics. The use of only one spectral pattern per combination allows us to compute the distortions with a low complexity signal decomposition method. This means that our method must learn in advance the spectral pattern associated to each unique combination of notes for the score. To this end, a state-of-the-art supervised method based on NMF with Beta-divergence and Multiplicative Update (MU) rules [17] is used, but in this work, we propose to apply it on synthetic signal generated from the MIDI score instead of the real audio performance.

Let us define a signal model, based on the one proposed in [18], which is the matrix based definition of the one described in (1)

$$\mathbf{Y}(f, \tau) \approx \hat{\mathbf{Y}}(f, \tau) = \mathbf{B}(f, k)\mathbf{G}(k, \tau) \quad (9)$$

where $\mathbf{Y}(f, \tau)$ is the magnitude spectrogram of the synthetic signal, $\hat{\mathbf{Y}}(f, \tau)$ is the estimated spectrogram,

$\mathbf{G}(k, \tau)$ matrix represents the gain of the spectral pattern for combination k at frame τ (i.e. $\mathbf{R}^\top(k, \tau)$), and $\mathbf{B}(f, k)$ matrix, for $k = 1, \dots, K$, represents the spectral patterns for all the combinations of notes defined in the score.

3.3 Online Alignment Stage

3.3.1 Observation model

As explained in section 3.2, the spectral patterns $\mathbf{B}(f, k)$ for the K different combinations of notes are learned in advance using a MIDI synthesizer and kept fixed. Each spectral pattern models the spectrum of a unique combination.

Now, the aim is to compute the gain matrix $\mathbf{G}(k, t)$ and the cost matrix $\mathbf{D}(\tau, t)$ that measures the suitability of each combination of notes belonging to each MIDI time τ to be active at each frame t (referenced to the input signal) by analyzing the likelihood between the spectral patterns $\mathbf{B}(f, k)$ and the input signal spectrogram¹. Similar approach was used by Fritsch and Plumbey in [19], but they use one component per instrument and note plus some extra-components to model the residual sounds.

From the cost matrix $\mathbf{D}(\tau, t)$, a classical DTW approach can be applied to compute the alignment path. The computation procedure to obtain the values of $\mathbf{D}(\tau, t)$ is not included here because of space limitations, but it is fully explained at [18].

3.3.2 Path Computation

We use here a DTW based method to perform the alignment using the cost matrix $\mathbf{D}(\tau, t)$ obtained in section 3.3.1. This cost matrix is computed from the input signal $\mathbf{X}(f, t)$ and the “synthetic” spectral patterns per combination $\mathbf{B}(f, k)$ explained in section 3.2. The term “synthetic” comes from the fact that the spectral patterns $\mathbf{B}(f, k)$ are computed from the score using a MIDI synthesizer.

Details about the implementation of this method are given in Section 2.3. Although classic DTW method achieves the lowest computational cost, it remains offline, so that it is not suitable for partially unknown series.

As in [18], the online algorithm differs from the standard DTW algorithm in some points. Firstly, the signal is partially unknown (or the future of the signal is not known when making the alignment decisions), so the global path constraints cannot be directly implemented, in other words, the recursion backwards can not be traced from the last frame T of the signal. Secondly, the algorithm has a limitation in its anti-causal response. The latency of the algorithm (the delay in the decision) must be limited to a maximum value. Consequently, an incremental solution is required. The recursion backwards can be traced in equally spaced frames of the input signal making the latency equal to the difference in time of the frame when the backtracking is done and the input signal frame. Finally, in order to run in realtime, the complete algorithm should not increase the complexity with the length of the signal.

¹ Note that we are using \mathbf{X} and t instead of \mathbf{Y} and τ to represent the signal magnitude spectrogram and the time frames to distinguish between real world and synthetic signals.

Here, we propose an online algorithm with a fixed latency of just one frame. In order to obtain this low latency, no backtracking is allowed, taking the decision directly from the forward information at each frame t .

4. SEPARATION METHOD

Here the NMF factorization framework is composed of two parameters, the gains $g_{n,j}(t)$ and the spectral patterns $b_{n,j}(f)$, as described in Eq. (1), but it now includes more than one instrument, specified by index j . Algorithm 1 shows an overview of the separation system with fixed instrument models.

Algorithm 1 Separation Algorithm with fixed instrument models

- 1 Compute $X(t, f)$ from a the audio mixture to separation.
 - 2 Initialise gains $g_{n,j}(t)$ with the ground-truth pitch transcription and the basis functions $b_{n,j}(f)$ with the previously trained ones.
 - 3 **for** C iterations **do**
 - 4 Update gains $g_{n,j}(t)$.
 - 5 **end for**
-

The MIDI score-aligned information is used to initialize the gains $g_{n,j}(t)$ for the NMF factorization. A random positive value is given when the aligned MIDI score indicates that the corresponding pitch indexes of instrument j are active at frame t . The gains associated to non-active pitches of the instrument j at frame t are set to zero.

Once the gains $g_{n,j}(t)$ are initialised, and using the trained instrument models $b_{n,j}(f)$, an iterative algorithm is run as shown in Algorithm 1. This algorithm iteratively updates $g_{n,j}(t)$ according to Eq. (4), while keeping $b_{n,j}(f)$ fixed. Once the gains are estimated, the separated signals are computed using Wiener masks as described in [4].

Although the NMF factorization framework is intrinsically offline, when spectral patterns $b_{n,j}(f)$ are fixed, the only parameters to be updated are the gains $g_{n,j}(t)$. When using the updating equation, the gains at frame t just depend on the input signal $X(t, f)$ at frame t and, consequently, the algorithm becomes online.

5. EXPERIMENTS

5.1 Training and testing data

At the training stage (see Section 2.1), the spectral basis functions are estimated using the RWC musical instrument sound database [20]. Four instruments are studied in the experiments (violin, clarinet, tenor saxophone and bassoon). From the RWC database we select the files with one playing style (normal) and one dynamic level (mezzo), since this is the configuration used in the majority of published results.

The database proposed in [2] is used for the testing stage. The ground-truth alignment between MIDI and audio was interpolated from annotated beat times of the audio. The

annotated beats were verified by a musician through playing back the audio together with these beats as explained in [2].

5.2 Experimental set-up

5.2.1 Model parameters

The frame size and the hop size for the STFT are set to 128 ms and 32 ms respectively. Also, $C = 50$ iterations for the NMF-based algorithms is used.

In relation to the pitch resolution, in the training stage a pitch resolution of a semitone (the same as the training database) is used. In the separation stage, the learned basis functions $b_{n,j}(f)$ are adapted to a 1/8 semitone resolution in pitch by replicating the function for each semitone 8 times. Real instruments produce pitches not only at idealized semitones, due to pitch variations such as vibrato. With a 1/8 semitone resolution in pitch, we can better capture the pitch variation of real instruments. Here, $\beta = 1.5$ has been used as demonstrated in [4].

5.2.2 Testing metrics

For an objective evaluation of the source separation performance of the proposed method, we use the metrics implemented in [21] (BSS EVAL Toolbox 2.1). These metrics are commonly accepted by the research community in source separation, and therefore facilitate a fair evaluation of the method.

For the score alignment results, the MIREX ² metrics, which are the most used among the community, have been used.

5.3 Results

The proposed system has two main stages: Score Following and Source Separation. Firstly, the online alignment method is assessed in front of the offline version and other state-of-the-art proposal. Then, both alignment methods are tested into a common SSS framework.

5.3.1 Alignment method results

Figure 1 shows the performance of the proposed online Score Following method. It is compared to its corresponding offline version, Duan&Pardo [2] (non-DTW-based state-of-the-art method) and Oracle which shows the maximum accuracy from the ground-truth data. Oracle is not a score following system but the provided aligned MIDI score assuming constant tempo and perfect synchronization between musicians. It represents the evolution of the accuracy for each method while the correct aligned decision threshold moves from 50ms to 2000ms.

This test details that the ground-truth cannot be used as itself unless the considered threshold grows more than 200ms. This is because this data has been obtained by a common alignment between all the independent instrument signals from the data base. Regarding this limitation,

Figure 1. States-based Offline DTW with tempo constraint path estimation

Method	SDR	SIR	SAR
Oracle	16.54 dB	24.04 dB	17.32 dB
Proposed	12.85 dB	21.45 dB	14.67 dB
Duan&Pardo	11.94 dB	19.27 dB	13.11 dB

Table 1. SSS results with both alignment method and the Oracle ones. Audible examples are available at <http://anclas3.ujaen.es/onlineSSS/>

the proposed online method outperforms the state-of-the-art one. Besides, it has a minimum distance from the offline version, concerning that it only uses the forward side of the DTW algorithm.

5.3.2 Source Separation results

The aligned score from the proposed method and the one from [2] has also been tested over the Source Separation task. The Oracle signals for SSS are obtained by using the analysis/synthesis filter bank over the isolated signal, so that filter bank effects are avoided from the comparison. Here, both data sets have been used for initializing the gains matrixes as described in section 4 based on [4]. Then, results of each alignment method with a common SSS stage are shown in Table 1.

SSS results show the same tendency as in section 5.3.1. The proposed alignment method overcomes the state-of-the-art one with almost the equivalent difference as in section 5.3.1. Besides, the distance from Oracle results is not so big despite the alignment mistakes. This means that the SSS algorithm is using properly instrument models which are not causing so much distortion at the output signals.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The proposed alignment method has provided better results at the alignment assesment than the state-of-the art one. These results are also reflected at the SSS test where a better alignment provides better separation results. However, it can be seen that here the differences are lower. That could be caused because the lack or precision of the alignment stage would affect the whole note assesment in the alignment test but only a small note are (near the note onset) in the SSS test.

²http://www.music-ir.org/mirex/wiki/2015:Main_Page

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by the Andalusian Business, Science and Innovation Council under project P2010- TIC-6762 and (FEDER) the Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness under Projects TEC2012-38142- C04-01, TEC2012-38142- C04-03 and TEC2012-38142- C04-04.

7. REFERENCES

- [1] F. Rodriguez-Serrano, J. Carabias-Orti, P. Vera-Candeas, F. Canadas-Quesada, and N. Ruiz-Reyes, "Monophonic constrained non-negative sparse coding using instrument models for audio separation and transcription of monophonic source-based polyphonic mixtures," *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, vol. 72, no. 1, pp. 925–949, Apr. 2013.
- [2] Z. Duan and B. Pardo, "Soundprism: An online system for score-informed source separation of music audio," *Selected Topics in Signal Processing, IEEE Journal of*, vol. 5, no. 6, pp. 1205–1215, 2011.
- [3] J. Carabias-Orti, T. Virtanen, P. Vera-Candeas, N. Ruiz-Reyes, and F. Canadas-Quesada, "Musical Instrument Sound Multi-Excitation Model for Non-Negative Spectrogram Factorization," *Selected Topics in Signal Processing, IEEE Journal of*, vol. 5, no. 6, pp. 1144–1158, 2011.
- [4] F. Rodriguez Serrano, Z. Duan, P. Vera-Candeas, B. Pardo, and J. J. Carabias-Orti, "Online Score-Informed Source Separation with Adaptive Instrument Models," *Journal of New Music Research*, 2015.
- [5] Z. Duan, G. Mysore, and P. Smaragdis, "Online PLCA for real-time semi-supervised source separation," in *Proc Int Conf on Latent Variable Analysis and Signal Separation (LVA/ICA 2012)*, Apr. 2012, pp. 34–41.
- [6] C. Joder, F. Weninger, F. Eyben, D. Virette, and B. Schuller, "Real-time speech separation by semi-supervised nonnegative matrix factorization." in *Proc Int Conf on Latent Variable Analysis and Signal Separation (LVA/ICA 2012)*, Apr. 2012, pp. 322–329.
- [7] L. Simon and E. Vincent, "A general framework for online audio source separation," in *Proc Int Conf on Latent Variable Analysis and Signal Separation (LVA/ICA 2012)*, Apr. 2012, pp. 397–404.
- [8] S. Dixon, "Live tracking of musical performances using on-line time warping," in *Proc. Int. Conf. on Digital Audio Effects (DAFx)*, Madrid, Apr. 2005, pp. 92–97.
- [9] A. Cont, "A Coupled Duration-Focused Architecture for Real-Time Music-to-Score Alignment," *Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence, IEEE Transactions on*, vol. 32, no. 6, pp. 974–987, Jun. 2010.
- [10] T. Virtanen and A. Klapuri, "Analysis of polyphonic audio using source-filter model and non-negative matrix factorization," *Advances in Models for Acoustic Processing, Neural Information Processing Systems Workshop*, 2006.
- [11] E. Vincent, N. Bertin, and R. Badeau, "Adaptive Harmonic Spectral Decomposition for Multiple Pitch Estimation," *IEEE Transactions on Audio, Speech, and Language Processing*, vol. 18, no. 3, pp. 528–537, 2010.
- [12] C. Févotte and J. Idier, "Algorithms for nonnegative matrix factorization with the beta-divergence," *Neural Computation*, vol. 23, Mar. 2011.
- [13] D. Lee and H. Seung, "Algorithms for non-negative matrix factorization," *Advances in neural information processing systems*, pp. 556–562, 2001.
- [14] F. Itakura, "Minimum prediction residual principle applied to speech recognition," *Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing, IEEE Transactions on*, vol. 23, no. 1, pp. 67–72, 1975.
- [15] L. Rabiner and A. Rosenberg, "Considerations in dynamic time warping algorithms for discrete word recognition," *Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing, IEEE Transactions on*, vol. 26, pp. 575–582, 1978.
- [16] D. Berndt and J. Clifford, "Using Dynamic Time Warping to Find Patterns in Time Series." *KDD workshop*, pp. 359–370, 1994.
- [17] J. Carabias-Orti, M. Cobos, P. Vera-Candeas, and F. Rodriguez-Serrano, "Nonnegative signal factorization with learnt instrument models for sound source separation in close-microphone recordings," *EURASIP Journal on Advances in Signal Processing*, vol. 1, Apr. 2015.
- [18] J. Carabias-Orti, F. Rodriguez-Serrano, P. Vera-Candeas, F. Canadas-Quesada, and N. Ruiz-Reyes, "An audio to score alignment framework using factorization and Dynamic Time Warping," in *Proc 16th Int Society for Music Information Retrieval Conf (ISMIR)*, 2015.
- [19] J. Fritsch and M. Plumbley, "Score informed audio source separation using constrained nonnegative matrix factorization and score synthesis," in *Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP), 2013*, May 2013, pp. 888–891.
- [20] M. Goto, "Development of the RWC Music Database," in *Proceedings of the 18th International Congress on Acoustics (ICA 2004)*, 2004, pp. 553–556.
- [21] E. Vincent, "Musical source separation using time-frequency source priors," *IEEE Transactions on Audio, Speech, and Language Processing*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 91–98, 2006.